

PHASE ANGLE EFFECTS ON THERMO-MECHANICAL FATIGUE (TMF) IN A SINGLE CRYSTAL NICKEL SUPERALLOY

A. Gonzalez Garcia¹, J. Jones¹, R. Lancaster¹, M. Whittaker¹, S. John¹ & J. Mason-Flucke²

In hot-section components of jet engines, the overlay of cyclic mechanical and thermal loads can result in a complex failure mechanism known as Thermo-Mechanical Fatigue (TMF), where the combination of fatigue, creep, and oxidation damage can lead to the nucleation and propagation of cracks, and ultimately catastrophic failure. In this research, a series of TMF tests were undertaken on a single crystal nickel-based superalloy, CMSX-4, under a variety of phase angles (-180°, -135°, -90°, 90°, 45° & 0°) to understand the evolving damage mechanisms that can occur under the various loading conditions. The generated data has shown that for the strain ranges tested, fatigue life is significantly affected by the employed phase angle. Furthermore, the length of time that the material is exposed to elevated temperature also has a substantial influence on the material's microstructure, and thus, the dominant mode of damage that occurs.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past century the aviation industry has strived for continual innovation and considerable improvements have been made through technological change in various disciplines including materials, engines, airframes, controls and airline business models [1]. With the introduction of climate change initiatives such as the European ACARE "Flight Path 2050" [2], and the UK government's policy to reduce CO₂ emissions by 60 % by the year 2050 [3], research and innovation efforts in the aerospace industry have been focused on the development of more efficient jet engines. To achieve these targets the Turbine Entry Temperatures (TET) of modern jet engines have steadily increased in an attempt to increase their thermodynamic efficiency (as it allows the hydrocarbon fuel to be burnt at temperatures closer to its stoichiometric value of 2500 K [4]). However this is limited by the allowable structural temperature of the turbine components.

As such, gas stream temperatures have increased even above current turbine material melting temperatures, from less than 950 °C in early engine models in the 1930s [5], to approximately 1800 °C in modern engines such as the Trent 900 [6] due to improved cooling designs. Under increasingly arduous thermal and mechanical cycles hot section components of jet engines are susceptible to Thermo-Mechanical Fatigue (TMF), a complex damage mechanism involving creep, fatigue, and oxidation [7]. The service lives of turbine blades and nozzle guide vanes have long been predicted assuming isothermal low cycle fatigue (LCF) and creep conditions [8], [9], however this may not capture the different damage mechanisms that occur under TMF loading. Given the heterogeneous temperature fields and thermal transients within the first and second high pressure stages of gas turbines, turbine blade components are typically prone to TMF damage, with specifically susceptible locations along the blade geometry highlighted in Figure 1.

¹ Institute of Structural Materials, Swansea University, Bay Campus, Swansea, SA1 8E

² Rolls-Royce plc, Bristol, BS11JQ, UK. N, UK

FIGURE 1 Typical TMF load cycles of a turbine blade; $\phi \approx -135^\circ$ is observable for leading and trailing edge, where cracks are typically initiated. Reproduced from Mai [10].

Several studies have been reported on the TMF behaviour of single crystal turbine blade materials. Choi et al. [11] adopted a 450-850 °C temperature cycle, with in-phase (IP) (where peak stress coincides with the peak cycle temperature) and out-of-phase (OP) (where peak stress occurs at the minimum cycle temperature) TMF tests performed under $R_\epsilon = -1$ on CMSX-4. For IP TMF the stress response revealed cyclic softening, while OP presented cyclic hardening. Their ϵ -Nf curves were found to intersect at a given strain. Using limited data for CMSX-4 at a higher T_{Max} of 1000 °C, but similar conditions, Sun et al. [12] repeated this observation, however differences were found to be small between the two phase angles. Kraft and Mughrabi [13] found OP TMF to be more damaging than the IP and 90° cycles in [001] orientated CMSX-6 at 600-1100 °C under strain control conditions. This was attributed to an asymmetry of mechanical strain due to non-linear characteristics of thermal expansion. As such, the mechanical strain is less in the high-temperature half cycle than in the low-temperature portion of the cycle, which results in a more moderate degree of tensile stress and longer fatigue life for IP TMF. Both Han et al. (SR99, 400-900 °C, $R_\epsilon = -1$) [14], and Hong et al. (CMSX-4, 400-950 °C, $R_\epsilon = -1$) [15] corroborated lower lives for OP TMF compared to LCF performed at the equivalent T_{max} , and slightly shorter lives than IP TMF in the case of [14], where plastic strain amplitudes revealed the maximum tensile stress at the cold end of the OP cycle to be the life-limiting factor for OP TMF. In [15], OP TMF was found to exhibit a smaller plastic strain range and a lower mean stress. More recently, Segersall and Deng [16] tested different orientations of CMSX-4 at 100-850 °C under IP and OP TMF conditions, and found little difference in their respective lives at similar orientations.

Less is known about the multitude of intermediate phase angles between IP and OP and their behavioural trends. Okazaki and Sakaguchi [17] found, at 400°C-900 °C and $R_\epsilon = -1$, the CW90° diamond phase angle exhibits significantly longer lives than the almost equal IP and OP. Similar results were observed for CW90° by Sakaguchi and Okazaki [18], although IP was found to be slightly more damaging than OP across various strain ranges. Egly et al. [19] observed a factor of 8 increase in life with a -20° phase shift as opposed to IP TMF in [001] oriented CMSX-4 at 450-950 °C. In this test ϵ_{Max} occurs at approximately 880 °C, which is 70 °C lower than the IP tests. Even longer lives were found for non-constant strain rate TMF. The results were attributed to stress relaxation effects, which, since they are dependent on the time in which high temperature coincides with mechanical strain, vary for each loading condition. Coppola et al. [20] used a novel procedure to investigate the influence of phase angle on TMF lives of CMSX4 at 600-1050 °C at an $R_\epsilon = -1$. Firstly, the service conditions of an intermediate pressure blade (IPT) were simulated using finite element analysis, from which three regions were reproduced: namely the leading edge at the aerofoil

mid-height (A), the inner platform to aerofoil fillet (B) and the aerofoil inner zone (C). The conditions in regions B, where maximum tensile strain was induced at 950 °C compared to 700 °C in conditions A and C, were found to be the most detrimental on fatigue strength. The CCW 90° phase angle in region C was also found to have a harmful influence compared to region A. The curves for the different loading cycles were relatively parallel. Despite the temperature profiles being identical the hysteresis stress-strain loops differed significantly with compressive loops developing in A, and tensile loops in C. The authors commented that since the levels of plasticity dissipated under tension, as observed in condition C, this will have caused a more damaging effect, and as such, a reduction in the resulting TMF life [20].

As discussed, TMF is a complex phenomenon, with the contribution of each damage mechanism controlled by a multitude of factors. It is evident that the applied phase angle has a considerable influence on the TMF lives of single crystal superalloys, however there is limited research available studying the wider range of phase angles, and how they affect the underlying microstructure and mode of deformation in the material. This research will investigate the TMF behaviour of CMSX-4 under a wide variety of phase angles, supported by advanced monitoring capabilities, thorough microstructural evolution studies and fractographic investigations to establish how damage initiates, evolves and progresses in the alloy under the contrasting conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Material and Specimens

In this study, the second-generation nickel based single crystal superalloy, CMSX-4, was used. A series of CMSX-4 TMF specimens were manufactured from material blanks with grain growth aligned to be within 15° of the <001> direction. The chemical composition is displayed in Table 1.

CMSX-4 exhibits two main solid-solution face-centered cubic (FCC) phases: the primary γ -matrix and the secondary γ' -precipitates. The γ' -phase is ordered with the stoichiometric composition Ni₃(Al, Ti) in an L₁₂ structure, with a volume content of approximately 70 %. In this research, the material was subjected to a post-manufacture hot isostatic pressing (HIP) procedure to reduce the presence of casting porosity features, followed by a solution heat treatment to dissolve the γ/γ' eutectic, and cooled via gas fan quench. The material was then double aged at 1140°C for 2 hours and 870 °C for 16 hours to produce a regular cuboidal γ' microstructure.

TABLE 1 Chemical composition (in weight%) of CMSX-4.

Alloy	Cr	Co	Mo	W	Ta	Re	Nb	Al	Ti	Hf	Ni	Density
CMSX-4	6.4	9.6	0.6	6	6.5	3	-	5.6	1	0.1	Bal.	8.70

Mechanical Test Method

Thermo-Mechanical Fatigue (TMF) tests were performed under strain-controlled conditions on a 50kN servo-hydraulic test frame with an induction coil capability to provide the appropriate thermal cycles, controlled by infra-red pyrometry, each in accordance to ISO 12111:2011 [21]. TMF tests were performed with a triangular shaped loading and temperature waveform, under R=-∞ loading conditions with heating and cooling rates of 16.67 °C/s-1. A temperature cycle of 550-1050 °C was employed with applied strain ranges between 0.5 and 1.2 %. An example of the strain temperature

paths at $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.95\%$ for the various phase angles at 550-1050 °C is given in Figure 2. In this plot the 90° test travels clockwise around the loop (CW 90°), whilst the -90° goes counterclockwise around it (CCW 90°)

FIGURE 2 Strain vs temperature $R=-\infty$ TMF waveforms for $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.95\%$.

The tensile force drop method was used to determine the failure of each test. Using this method, the specimen is considered to have failed when there is typically a 10 % force drop from the stabilised peak tensile force. In the case of continuously softening test conditions, failure was determined from the projected straight-line locus of stabilised peak tensile stress versus cycles. Upon the determination of failure, test temperature was reduced to ambient, and the specimen was cycled until separated into two. Any sample that endured the set runout number of cycles was unloaded and not retested.

Temperature Control

Accurate temperature control of a metallic surface using pyrometry can only be achieved once the surface emissivity of the target is stable. The emissivity of CMSX-4 at 1050 °C was calibrated in previous work by the same authors [22]. This included a rigorous specimen cleaning procedure prior to heating the specimen to 1050 °C and holding at temperature for 7.8 hours. This produced a fully stabilised oxide on the surface and a consistent emissivity value of 0.54.

Given the solid cylindrical nature of the TMF test specimens, prior to any experimentation a verification study was carried out to understand whether a temperature gradient existed between the internal central core and the external surface of the $\varnothing 6$ mm specimen used in this study. A 1 mm diameter hole was drilled through a specimen to allow a type N thermocouple to be placed inside. Additional thermocouples were then welded to the external surface. External and internal temperatures were compared across three ramp rates, 5, 10 and 20 °C/s-1. The thermal profile was recorded using spot welded thermocouples across the 12mm gauge section. A pyrometer controlled the temperature using the emissivity value of 0.54, producing the temperature profiles that fell within the limits defined in the governing TMF standard [21].

It is recognised that both in the heating and cooling parts of the cycle a thermal lag may exist between the centre of the specimen and the surface, due to the induction heating and forced air cooling. Whilst this effect is unavoidable, the magnitude will be dependent on the heating and cooling rates. Therefore these rates were optimised to provide a rate which allows for a reduced cycle time,

in conjunction with minimising the gradient between specimen surface and centre. Experiments showed that a specimen rate of 16.67 °C/sec provided optimised conditions. Figure 3 displays the overall thermal expansion behaviour for this cycle at 550-1050 °C, in line with behaviour observed elsewhere in the literature for CMSX-4 [22].

FIGURE 3 Thermal expansion profile for the 16.67 °C/s⁻¹ thermal cycle.

Infra-red thermography (IRT) has previously been used by the authors for temperature control during thermal cycling under TMF conditions, with greater detail provided in previous articles [23], [24]. In this research IRT was trialled as a method of capturing crack initiation behaviour. Since the data accumulated from the IRT images was not calibrated, it was only possible to make comparisons between the specimens tested in this study, and it is not anticipated that such information could be extrapolated towards other work. In the IRT study, a single image was taken during each cycle, starting on the first cycle at maximum tensile strain. The number of cycles taken to detect the onset of surface cracking, and after fixed interval crack lengths of 0.5 mm and 1 mm, were recorded, with examples provided later in Figure 6.

Microstructural Analysis

Post-testing, samples of interest were extracted from specimens subjected to selected phase angles at $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.95\%$, $R = -\infty$, and 550-1050 °C in both the (001) and (010) planar orientations, as shown in Figure 8 b), using a Brillant 220 precision wet abrasive cut-off machine. These were then mounted, polished, and electro-etched using a 10% phosphoric acid solution and a 3 V voltage. Three images were taken from each sample at a set distance from the edges using a JEOL 7800F FEG-SEM microscope at x5000 magnification with a 10 kV accelerating voltage, and a 10mm working distance.

A Gaussian blur with a 5-pixel kernel was used to denoise the 2560x1048 pixel images, which were then turned into binaries by means of the automated Otsu algorithm. To estimate the degree of coarsening the ratio of the perimeter to the area of the image covered by the γ' -precipitates was measured in both directions and the average was taken. To quantify the directionality of the γ' -precipitates, horizontal and vertical lines were plotted over the longitudinal images at regular, 80-pixel intervals, and the number of intersections with the γ' -precipitates were counted. The parameter R , as previously defined by Sakaguchi and Okazaki [25], was calculated according to equation 1.

$$R = \log_{10} \left(\frac{H/H_0}{V/V_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where H and V are the number of intersections between the γ' phase and the lines perpendicular and parallel to the loading axis respectively, and H_0 and V_0 are the corresponding values for the virgin material. Through this method, the direction and the extent of the directional coarsening are quantified by the sign and the absolute value of R , respectively [25]. The R value is negative in the plate-like “N-type” microstructure, while positive in the rod-like “P-type”.

RESULTS

Experimental Results

The results from the TMF tests at $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.95\%$ are displayed in Table 2, together with additional LCF data at $1050\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Two different waveforms were used for the isothermal experiments, namely a triangular waveform to complement the conditions of the TMF tests (0.01667 Hz), and a standard 0.25 Hz trapezoidal waveform to compare with results from previous internal programmes. The TMF results across a variety of strain ranges between 0.5% and 1.2% support the observations on comparing across the 0.95% strain range tests. The SN curves as plotted in a $\Delta\varepsilon$ - N_f graph reveal relatively similar gradients for most phase angles, with none of the curves overlapping or intersecting each other, and similar behaviour is observed on a stabilised stress range condition. As can be seen across a common strain range of 0.95% , the 45° test is shown to have the longest fatigue life as compared to the tests on other phase angles and isothermal equivalents. However, since only a single data point was generated under this condition, caution should be taken when looking to establish a definitive conclusion based on this result. The next best performing phase angles are the diamond cycle in the counter-clockwise (-90°) then clockwise (90°) direction, both of which outperformed the more widely understood fully OP and IP regimes. This aligns with previous findings on TMF in CMSX-4 under IP, OP and diamond phase angles which also show diamond cycle tests outlasting the LCF isothermal equivalent tests performed at $T_{\text{Max}} = 900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [18].

CCW 90° TMF tests on uncoated CMSX-4 samples have been found to exhibit longer lives than CW 90° tests [20], which has been attributed to CCW loops developing in compression, whilst CW loops are mainly in tension, which is regarded as a more damaging form of deformation. This is corroborated in the current study as shown in Figure 4 b), where the stabilised CW loops consistently sit above the CCW loops, reaching a higher mean stress and therefore, spending more time under a tensile load. This is also true for the fully OP cycle, which experiences the most cyclic hardening of all six phase angles, which in turn results in the lowest fatigue life. This can be seen more clearly in Figure 4 c), where the OP test reaches a peak mean stress of approximately 350 MPa , whereas the two diamond shaped cycles predominantly deform under compression. Interestingly, the IP cycle exhibits the lowest positioned stabilised strain-stress loop of the six regimes, yet is the second most damaging phase angle after the OP. As mentioned in the introduction [19], a -20° phase shift TMF test, despite exhibiting a significantly higher degree of plastic deformation, has been shown to have a far superior response compared to IP TMF. Such findings were replicated in the current study with the IP hysteresis mechanical strain-stress loops being predominantly closed in the first cycle as seen in Figure 4 a) despite the lower lives for IP TMF, which suggests fatigue-creep interactions causing damage within the sample.

Like the IP test, the 45° sample also exhibits limited evidence of plastic deformation in the hysteresis loops, as opposed to the diamond, OP and -135° cycles which all show varying degrees of plasticity in the monotonic cycle. In the diamond cycles, it is worth noting that in these regimes, ε_{Max} occurs at $800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a temperature at which high temperature damage mechanisms such as creep

and oxidation begin to become more prevalent in this alloy. These effects become more significant as the phase angle deviates to -135° and the peak compressive strain occurs at 937.5°C . The contribution of creep deformation is clear, since as the material is unloaded from a peak compressive strain, creep damage coincides with elastic unloading and the gradient of the curve is steeper than would otherwise be anticipated. Furthermore, in the OP test, on compressive loading the magnitude of the compressive stress actually begins to decrease as creep deformation exceeds elastic loading.

A further observation of the stabilised hysteresis behaviour (Figure 4 b) is that the mode of deformation across the different phase angles is now predominantly elastic, with little width to the loops. However, it is also noticeable that the modulus does vary as a function of temperature, and hence they do not appear as linear as they would under isothermal conditions.

TABLE 2 TMF test results for CMSX-4 at $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.95\%$, $R = -\infty$, and $550\text{-}1050^\circ\text{C}$, and equivalent isothermal LCF tests at 1050°C

Phase Angle	0°	45°	90°	-180°	-135°	-90°	-135° 120 s Dwell at Tmax	LCF Trapezoidal	LCF Triangle
Normalised Cycles to Failure	0.751	10.631 (runout)	1.874	0.313	0.679	6.714	0.519	0.687	1.000
Normalised Stabilised Stress Range	0.657	0.625	0.624	0.706	0.674	0.661	0.670	0.568	0.398

FIGURE 4 Comparison of the stress vs mechanical strain cycles for the various TMF phase angles tested under an applied $\Delta\varepsilon$ of 0.95% a) monotonic cycle, b) stabilised cycle ($N_f/2$), c) Comparison of the mean stress evolution for the various TMF phase angles tested under an applied $\Delta\varepsilon$ of 0.95% .

Fracture Behaviour

Figure 5 presents the fracture morphologies for the different phase angles, all of which were tested under an applied $\Delta\varepsilon$ of 0.95% and $R=-\infty$. Of the six phase angles, the IP test can be seen to exhibit a quasi-cleavage type fracture, with several features more associated with brittle type failures, such as a relatively flat surface, but with the added presence of ductile dimpling, resulting from the increased presence of creep during the test. This is contrary to the appearance of the OP cycle (Figure 5 a)), where there is no sign of creep damage on the surface but there is the increased presence of crystallographic features and a brittle mode of failure. This is reflected by the flatter nature of the

fracture surface, whilst failure appears to have initiated within the inherently brittle, external oxide layer. This morphology is also seen in the -135° (Figure 5 b)) and CCW 90° tests (Figure 5 d)) which also exhibit a larger degree of oxidation and multiple surface breaking initiation sites. Similarly, the fractographic behaviour of CW 90° also offers a similar morphology, with multiple surface breaking sites of fatigue initiation being present. However, in this sample, it appears that four neighbouring sites have coalesced and have propagated further into the material than that seen in the other phase angles. Despite this behaviour, there is little evidence in the experimental data of anything of discernible difference being evident in this test, as opposed to the others.

FIGURE 5 Keyence fractographic images and close-ups of initiation sites for a) OP, b) -135° , c) CW 90° , d) ACW 90° , e) 45° , and f) IP from left to right and top to bottom. Captured via Keyence microscopy. All tests performed under an applied $\Delta\varepsilon$ of 0.95 %.

Thermography - Initiation Behaviour

To address the initiation behaviour across the six samples in further depth, thermography and acoustic emissions were employed to identify whether crack initiation occurred after a similar number of cycles, irrespective of the applied phase angle. In the TMF tests a thermal camera monitored the thermal profile over the gauge length of each sample to capture any temperature differences that may arise due to crack initiation. In each case, thermography was effective in capturing the first onset of crack initiation. Figure 6 presents some of the typical stills captured from the thermal imaging for the OP test at the point of ε_{MAX} in the 1st cycle, the cycle where crack initiation was first detected, the cycle where a 1mm crack was detected, and the final cycle prior to failure.

FIGURE 6 Thermal camera images captured from the OP TMF test after a) 1st cycle, b) 1st detection of crack initiation, c) 1 mm crack, d) Final cycle prior to failure.

From the information collected, a relationship deriving the life to first crack initiation could be established as a proportion of the total TMF life for each respective sample as can be seen in Table 3. It is clear for all samples that the first cracks are detected very early in the test and as such the majority of the fatigue life of these tests is predominantly associated with the crack propagation stage. This consistent behaviour is evidenced by the relationship displayed in Figure 7 (a-c), which shows an estimate of the number of cycles to the first fatigue crack, cycles to 0.5 mm crack and cycles to 1 mm crack size, for all tests where thermal imaging was used across the six phase angles.

TABLE 3 TMF initiation life data from thermal imaging.

FIGURE 7 Relationship between TMF life and number of cycles to a) first initiation, b) 0.5 mm crack length and c) 1 mm crack length, based on images collected from thermal imaging.

As shown by the different plots in Figure 7, there is a clear relationship between detectable crack size and the life of the samples, which becomes stronger with larger crack sizes. Such behaviour provides added confidence that thermal imaging can indeed be employed as an effective tool of detecting the early signs of crack initiation, and also monitoring subsequent crack growth. However, it is important to note that despite the positive findings identified through using thermography to detect the early stages of crack initiation, this approach does require a crack to nucleate at the surface, for the camera to be situated in an appropriate location to capture the initiation, and that the size of the crack is dictated by the resolution of the camera used.

Rafting - Microstructure Evolution

For the current testing conditions all samples present a certain degree of rafting, since the samples experience sufficiently high thermal exposures, and the threshold strain, previously found to be in the region of 0.1 % by Matan et al. [26], for rafting to occur is exceeded. As can be seen from Figure 8 a) there is a logarithmic relationship between the time at temperature, in this case represented by the test time, and the degree of rafting as measured from the ratio of the total perimeter of the γ' phase divided by the area.

There is a considerable spread between different phase angles regardless of test time, particularly between the 90° and -90° samples, indicating that other factors might affect the kinetics of this phenomenon. The hold time at maximum temperature experienced by the -135° dwell sample seems to have affected the degree of coarsening only insofar as it increases the proportion of the test time that the sample spends at maximum temperature. Similarly the isothermal samples present a greater degree of coarsening since they spend the entirety of the test at 1050°C .

FIGURE 8 Relationship between ratio of γ' precipitate perimeter over area (average of transverse and longitudinal images) and test duration with standard deviations for images measured within a sample b) examples of IP, virgin, and OP microstructure.

Under the effect of the applied stresses at maximum temperature the morphological changes as measured by the parameter R correspond to those expected for superalloys having negative lattice misfit like CMSX-4, with N-type rafting when the peak cycle temperature coincides with a stabilised tensile stress, and P-type rafting when it coincides with a stabilised compressive stress as shown in Figure 9 a). Since the samples analysed presented different lives, and therefore different lengths of time at temperature, the results were normalised in Figure 9 b) by dividing R by the normalized test time, which revealed a very close linear correlation with a weighted R-squared value of 0.934.

Low temperature deformation behaviour does not seem to be the determinant factor in these morphological changes, since the relaxation of the lattice misfit strain and reduction in γ/γ' interfacial coherency, the fundamental requirements for rafting to occur, take place at higher temperatures,

whereas at low temperatures mechanisms such as slip band shearing tend to dominate. Further analysis will be performed on samples with similar lives and different phase angles to elucidate the cause and effect of rafting on TMF behaviour.

FIGURE 9 a) Relationship between R and average stabilised Stress at peak temperature b) normalized by test duration.

CONCLUSIONS

From the results presented in this paper it is evident that the applied phase angle exerts a substantial influence on the overall life and the underlying damage and deformation mechanisms operating under TMF, with IP, OP, and to a lesser extent -135° being more damaging than the equivalent LCF cycle at $T_{\max} = 1050^\circ\text{C}$ and a similar applied strain range.

Furthermore, the contrast in life and fractographic appearance between the CCW and CW 90° tests highlights the effect that cycle direction has on deformation and oxidation behaviour in TMF of single crystal nickel superalloys, which is identified as an area for future analysis.

Infra-red thermography has been successfully trialled as a monitoring technique, with preliminary findings indicating that crack initiation occurs relatively early at the strain ranges and conditions tested, and that the majority of each TMF test is spent under crack propagation.

Under the test conditions employed in the current study significant γ' precipitate coarsening is observed, with the degree being proportional to the time spent at temperature, and the phase angle and direction having an effect on the kinetics of the morphological process. In TMF the rafting regime is markedly dependent on the stabilised stress state at high temperature, with N-type rafts developing under tension, and P-type rafts developing under compression for negative misfit nickel-based superalloys.

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Muller, R. and Pelfrene, P., *Create: Creating innovative air transport technologies for Europe*, EASN, FP7/2007-2013, 2010.
- (2) Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport (European Commission), *“Flightpath 2050 - Europe’s Vision for Aviation”*, ISBN 978-92-79-29/24-6, 2011.
- (3) Department of the Environment, *“Climate Change: The UK programme summary: <https://www.cne-siar.gov.uk/media/5820/climate-change-uk-programme-summary.pdf>”*, 2000.
- (4) Boyce, M., *Gas Turbine Engineering Handbook*, 4th ed., Butterworth-Heinemann, 2011.

- (5) G. Drew, “*Thermo-mech Fatigue of the Single Crystal Superalloy CMSX-4*”, Cambridge, 2004.
- (6) Whittaker, M., Lancaster, R., Harrison, W., Pretty, C., and Williams, S., *Materials*, Vol. 6, No. 11, 2013, pp. 5275–5290.
- (7) Pahlavanyali, S., Drew, G., Rayment, A., and Rae, C., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 30, No. 2 2008, pp. 330–338.
- (8) Kamaraj, M., Sadhana, *Acad. Proc. Eng. Sci.*, Vol. 28, No. 1–2, 2003, pp. 115–128.
- (9) Evans, W. J., Lancaster, R., Steele, A., Whittaker, M., and Jones, N., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 31, No. 11–12, 2009, pp. 1709–1718.
- (10) Mai, R., *Thermo-mechanical fatigue investigations on nickel based superalloys and creep of NiAl thin films*, Heriot Watt University, 2011.
- (11) Choi, J., Wee, S., Koo, J.-M., Chung, E.-S., Kwon, S.-H., and Seok, C.-S., *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*, Vol. 34, No. 5, 2020, pp. 1855–1862.
- (12) Sun, J., Yang, S., and Yuan, H., *Mat. Science and Engineering: A*, Vol. 809, 2021, p. 140918.
- (13) Kraft, S. and Mughrabi, H., *Thermomech. Fatigue Behavior of Mat.*, Vol. 2, 1996, pp. 27-40.
- (14) Han, G. M., Yu, J. J., Sun, X. F., and Hu, Z. Q., *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, Vol. 528, No. 19–20, 2011, pp. 6217–6224.
- (15) Hong, H. U., Kang, J. G., Choi, B. G., Kim, I. S., Yoo, Y. S., and Jo, C. Y., *Int J Fatigue*, Vol. 33, No. 12, 2011, pp. 1592–1599.
- (16) Segersäll, M., and Deng, D., *Int J Fatigue*, Vol. 146, May 2021, p. 106162.
- (17) Okazaki, M., and Sakaguchi, M., *Int J Fatigue*, Vol. 30, No. 2, 2008, pp. 318–323.
- (18) Sakaguchi, M., and Okazaki, M., *JSME Int. Journal Series A*, Vol. 49, No. 3, 2006, p. 345–354.
- (19) Egly, T., Lang, K., and Lohe, D., *Int J Fatigue*, Vol. 30, No. 2, 2008, pp. 249–256.
- (20) Coppola, T., Riscifuli, S., Tassa, O. and Pasquero, G., *J. Eng. Gas Turbine Power*, Vol. 132, No. 1, 2010, pp. 12101/01-12101/05
- (21) Metallic materials — Fatigue testing — Strain-controlled thermomechanical fatigue testing method, ISO12111:2011, 2011.
- (22) Epishina A. I., and Lisovenko., *Mechanics of Solids*, Vol. 58, 2023, pp. 1587–1598.
- (23) Palmer, J., Jones J., Dyer A., Smith R., Lancaster R., and Whittaker M., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 121, 2019, pp. 208-218.
- (24) Jones, J., Brookes S., Whittaker M., and Lancaster R., *Materials Science and Technology*, Vol. 30, No. 15, 2014, pp. 1862-1876.
- (25) Sakaguchi, M., Okazaki, M., *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, Vol 534, 2012, pp.253-259.
- (26) Matan, N., Cox, D.C., Rae, C.M.F., et al., *Acta Materialia*, Vol. 47, 1999, pp. 2031-2045.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This information/report/data was generated under ATI Programme 113180. The provision of materials and supporting information from Rolls-Royce plc. is gratefully acknowledged.